

residue extracted with ethyl acetate to remove the unreacted starting oxime. The aqueous layer was made acidic with dil. aq. HCl to yield the desired carboxymethoximes (40-90%).

Reaction of ketones with 2-(aminoxy)acetic acid hemihydrochloride: A solution of appropriate ketone (0.01 mol), 2-(aminoxy)acetic acid hemihydrochloride (0.01 mol) and sodium acetate (0.03 mol) in ethanol (60 ml) was refluxed for 18-20 hrs. The solvent was removed under vacuo, and the residue extracted with ethyl acetate. The organic layer was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and concentrated to yield the desired carboxymethoximes (40-90%).

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Flavonoids of *Ipomoea dissecta*

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*IPOMOEA dissecta*¹ Willd. [syn. *I. optica* (L.) Roth.] belonging to the Convolvulaceae is reported to contain chlorogenic acid in the leaves². *I. fistulosa* has been recorded to contain kaempferol in the flowers³ and β -sitosterol in the leaves⁴. We now report the chemical components of the flowers of *I. dissecta*.

Fresh flowers (75 g) of *I. dissecta* collected from the Regional Engineering College Campus, Tiruchirapalli during late winter were extracted with hot 80% EtOH under reflux and the combined extract concentrated *in vacuo* and the aqueous concentrate fractionated successively into petrol (60-80°), ether and ethylacetate (EtOAc) solubles. The petrol fraction did not yield any crystalline solid.

The residue (0.1 g) from the ether fraction on crystallisation from Me₂CO yielded a yellow solid

(0.06 g) m.p. 277-79°, tetraacetate, m.p. 185-87° and was identified as kaempferol by R_f, colour reactions, uv and direct comparison with an authentic sample.

The residue (0.05 g) from the EtOAc fraction was dissolved in methanol and was subjected to preparative PC (Whatman No. 3, 15% HOAc) and the methanolic eluate of the only band that separated had λ_{\max} (MeOH) 243 (sh), 251 (sh), 268, 323 (sh), 365 nm; $\Delta\lambda$ (NaOMe)+50 nm; $\Delta\lambda$ (AlCl₃) and $\Delta\lambda$ (AlCl₃/HCl)+59 nm; $\Delta\lambda$ (NaOAc) nil (band II) and $\Delta\lambda$ (NaOAc/H₃BO₃) nil and responded to all the reactions expected of a flavone glycoside. It could be hydrolysed easily with 7% H₂SO₄ (100°, 2 hr) to yield kaempferol and glucose in almost equal quantities. The glycoside could therefore be identified as kaempferol-7-glucoside by R_f and uv data and the identity confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample.

This appears to be the first record of isolation of kaempferol and its 7-glucoside from *I. dissecta*.

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Antibacterial and Antialgal Activity of N-Isonicotinylamido-N'-Aryl/Guanidines

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CERTAIN alkyl/aryl guanidines or diaryl guanidine derivatives of isonicotinic acid hydrazide have been prepared with a view to evaluating their antibacterial activity. Isonicotinic acid hydrazide has been reacted with aryl amidine chlorides¹ in chloroform solution of the respective arylcyanamide² to afford hydrochloride salts (I and II). The

TABLE—N-ISONICOTINYL-N', N''-ARYL/ALKYL GUANIDINES

Sl. No.	R	R''	Mol. Formula*	M. P. °C	Picrate m.p. °C	% yield	I. R. frequencies (cm ⁻¹)
1	H	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₅ OCl	109	148	91	3250w (NH); 1680s -CONH; 1620s and 1590m guanidine, 840s guanidine
2	H	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₅ OCl ₂	232	215	85	3200m NH; 1680s -CONH; 1620-1600m guanidine, 860, guanidine
3	H	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₅ OCl	170	222	89	3450m NH; 1650s -CONH; 1620m and 860w guanidine
4	H	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₅ OCl ₂	195**	125	83	
5	H	<i>m</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₅ OCl ₃	215	175	90	3300w NH, 1700m -CONH, 1660-1620 and 850s guanidine; 710w C-Cl
6	H	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₅ OCl ₃	175	180	87	3375m NH; 1740s -CONH; 1680s and 820 guanidine, 760w C-Cl
7	H	<i>n</i> -Butyl	C ₁₁ H ₁₈ N ₅ OCl	250(d)	-	82	
8	H	Isopropyl	C ₁₀ H ₁₆ N ₅ OCl	250(d)	-	80	
9	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₅ OCl	206	-	75	
10	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₅ O	165	-	78	
11	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ N ₅ O	195	-	86	
12	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	C ₂₁ H ₂₂ N ₅ OCl	236	-	88	3250m -NH; 1060s, N-C(=N)-N; 1580s, 1620s, N-C=N; 1620s CO; 2527s, NH ₂ ⁺ Cl ⁻
13	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ N ₅ OCl ₂	223	-	76	3250m NH ⁽⁺⁾ ; 1032s, N-C(=N)-N; 1590w, N-C=N; 1630wCO

* The analytical data are within the admissible limits of experimental error.
 ** Hygroscopic.

alkylcyanamides and diaryl carbo-diimides were reacted with isoniazid. After refluxing the contents for one hour, dry hydrogen chloride gas was passed when respective guanidine hydrochlorides were obtained. These were characterised by elemental analysis and IR spectra.

Where R = Alkyl or aryl groups

Ar = aryl groups

The compounds were tested for antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *Klebsiella*, *pneumoniae*, *Aeromonas hydrophila*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus faecalis*, *Proteus mirabilis* and *Proteus vulgaris* and were found inactive at a conc. of 200 µg/ml. In a test for inhibition of growth of the blue-green alga *Anacystis nidulans*, *o*-Tolyl derivative (2, Table 1) exhibited the greatest activity and inhibited its growth at a conc. or 10 µg/ml.

(1) Preparation of N-Isonicotinylamido-N'-alkyl/N', N''-diaryl Guanidines :

The required alkyl cyanamides/1, 3-diaryl carbo-diimides were obtained by complete desulfurisation

of corresponding alkyl or 1,3-diaryl thiocarbamides with yellow lead oxide in acetone on a water-bath for about one hour. The black lead sulphide was filtered. The filtrate containing alkyl cyanamide/1, 3-diaryl carbo-diimide was treated with equivalent amount of isonicotinic acid hydrazide and dry hydrogen chloride gas was passed for 5 minutes. A solid separated out which was filtered and gave the expected products. These were recrystallised from ethanol. These results are presented in the Table.

(2) Preparation of N-Isonicotinylamido-N'-Aryl Guanidines :

The aryl amidine chlorides were prepared by passing dry hydrochloric acid gas in chloroform solution of the respective aryl cyanamide. These were obtained by desulfurisation of aryl thiocarbamides with lead acetate in alkaline medium. The lead sulphide was filtered off and the alkaline filtrate was neutralised with cold glacial acetic acid. The precipitated cyanamide was extracted with chloroform. Isoniazid dissolved in acetone was added. In some cases the reaction products were obtained immediately, while in others refluxing of the reaction mixture for half an hour was necessary to complete the reaction. The products were filtered, dried and m.p. determined. Picrates were

prepared from their aqueous or ethanolic solutions. The results are summarised in Table.

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Composition of Essential Oil of *Thymus serpyllum* Linn.

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THYMUS serpyllum Linn., widely distributed in Kumaon region of U. P. between 1600 and 3000 m, is used indigenously against the complaints of stomach, liver, kidney and vision. The work, so far, reported on essential oil of *Thymus serpyllum* shows that the chemical composition varies depending on the extrinsic factors¹⁻³. The authors⁴ earlier reported 17 compounds viz., α -pinene, camphene, β -pinene, car-3-ene, α -terpinene, limonene, 1,3-cineole, γ -terpinene, *p*-cymene, terpinolene, *trans*- β -terpineol, terpinen-4-ol, geraniol, traces of citronellal and linalool, thymol and carvacrol besides 6 unidentified compounds in the oil extracted from young plant material of *Thymus serpyllum*. The present communication relates to the analysis of the essential oil of fully matured plant to get detailed knowledge of the volatile constituents and to find out the change in composition of the oil in different seasons.

The essential oil was extracted from fresh plant material by steam distillation. The oil was separated

from the distillate with pet. ether (60-80°), dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and solvent was distilled off. Pet. ether solution of the oil (5 g) was treated with aq. sodium hydroxide (5%). The aqueous layer was separated, neutralized and extracted with ether. The phenols (3.1 g) were recovered by evaporating the solvent⁴. The phenolic mixture was cooled and the crystals formed were separated. The solid and liquid phenols were purified, their characteristic derivatives prepared and were identified as thymol (phenylurethane m.p. 106°; 3,5-dinitrobenzoate m.p. 102.5°) and carvacrol (phenylurethane m.p. 134°; 3,5-dinitrobenzoate m.p. 76°) respectively.

The oil free from phenols was analysed using the combined GC-MS instrument under the following conditions:

A 25 meter glass capillary column (i.d. 0.3 mm) coated with FFAP in Carlo Erba 2300 gas chromatograph was coupled with JEOL JMS-D 300 mass spectrometer through the glass interface which was further attached to JMA-2000 data system. 0.3 μ l of the sample was injected (injection split ratio 1:100). The column temperature was maintained at 60° for first six minutes, raised to 100° and then programmed at 4° per minute upto 180°. The injection, interface and ion source temperatures were 250°, 220° and 230° respectively. The ionization energy used was 70 eV. The spectra were scanned at 2.5 seconds interval. The reconstructed total ion chromatogram and mass spectra were plotted by the computer.

The chromatogram of the oil is presented in the Figure. The compounds corresponding to the peaks,

Fig. Gas chromatogram of *Thymus serpyllum* Oil

identified by their mass spectra and GC, are given in the Table.

The phenols are the principal constituents of the oil (thymol 60% and carvacrol 2%). The monoterpene hydrocarbons, sesquiterpene hydrocarbons, alcohols, esters and ketones constituted 18%, 7%, 8%, 2%, and 2% of the oil respectively. Terpinen-4-ol and *trans*- β -terpineol were found to be absent in the oil from the matured plant and the percentage